

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.0 Visions database analysis strategy/ IPBES Transformative Change Assessment

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Description: The review corresponds to the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment. The IPBES scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that Chapter 2 should examine the implications of different visions for sectors, sub-systems (including economic/market, financial, political, legal/judicial, educational, Indigenous and local systems, and ecosystems) and the interactions between them, at different spatial scales.

In this context, collected visions were coded drawing on Miles and Huberman's methodological approach (Miles & Huberman 1994). The coded visions were analysed using multi-factor analyses on purpose, direct and indirect drivers, followed by K-means clustering (Blasius & Greenacre, 2014). A sentiment analysis was also performed to gauge the attitudes, opinions, and emotions conveyed in the vision descriptions. Additionally, subjectivity scores were calculated to assess the degree of opinion and emotion reflected in these texts.

Process overview

Protocol

Step 1: Sentiment analysis of visions descriptions

Description: To investigate the sentiment of the descriptions within the 881 visions, *TextBlob library*, a popular Python tool for processing textual data, was used (Loria S., 2018). TextBlob provides a simple Application Programming Interface for common natural language processing tasks, including sentiment analysis. The library is particularly useful for quick and efficient sentiment evaluations due to its integration with the PatternAnalyzer from the pattern library, which is based on a lexicon of pre-scored words.

Method: Before performing sentiment analysis, the text data was pre-processed to ensure quality and consistency. This included converting all text to lowercase, removing punctuation and stop words (common words like 'and', 'the', etc., that do not contribute to sentiment), and tokenizing the text into individual words.

Each pre-processed text description was passed through TextBlob's sentiment analyzer. TextBlob evaluates the polarity and subjectivity of the text using a built-in sentiment lexicon. The lexicon contains words associated with positive and negative sentiments and their respective polarity scores. These metrics were used to infer the general tone and objectivity of the content in the visions. The polarity is represented by a number within the range [-1.0, 1.0], where 1 means a highly positive sentiment and -1 means a highly negative sentiment. The polarity score of 0.122 suggests a generally positive sentiment across the visions. The subjectivity is coded by a number a float within the range [0.0, 1.0], where 0.0 is very objective and 1.0 is very subjective. The subjectivity score of 0.339 indicates that the descriptions maintain a moderate balance between personal opinions and factual information.

Data location and description: Polarity score column and subjectivity score column in database (A)

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.0_visions_ database_partial(A)

Step 2: K-Means Clustering Analysis

Description: The goal of this analysis was to categorize assessed visions into distinct clusters based on their attributes, which are relevant for a sustainable world for nature and people.

The dataset consisted of various visions, each characterized by binary attributes (Yes/No), such as Species, Ecosystems, Biodiversity, Global Sustainability, Nature's Contribution to People, Quality of Life, Equity, Empowerment, Indigenous and Local Knowledge, Land Use Change, Sea Use, Climate Change, Pollution, Natural Resources Use, Invasive Species, Values, Demography, Technology, Economics, and Governance. Each vision also belongs to a specific cluster.

Method: The procedure follows the subsequent steps:

- Data Preparation

The dataset was loaded from an Excel file using the *pandas library* in Python. Binary attributes (Yes/No) were converted to numerical values (1/0) to facilitate clustering analysis.

- Clustering with K-Means

K-means clustering was used to group the visions into four distinct clusters based on their attributes. The Cluster column in the dataset indicated the cluster each vision belongs to. The *pandas* and *numpy* libraries were used for data manipulation and processing. The *matplotlib* library was used for creating radar plot visualizations.

- Grouping and Averaging

The dataset was grouped by the Cluster column using the group by function from the *pandas* library. The mean of each attribute for each cluster was calculated to understand the central tendency of each cluster's characteristics.

- Choice of relevant clusters

The choice of four clusters was based on the results of the Elbow Method, which is a common technique used to determine the optimal number of clusters. This method involves plotting the within-cluster sum of squares against the number of clusters and identifying the point where the rate of decrease sharply slows down (the "elbow" point). For our dataset, the elbow point indicated that four clusters provided a good balance between minimizing WCSS and avoiding overfitting.

- Description of the clusters

Each of the four clusters demonstrated distinct and meaningful characteristics. These differences are crucial for understanding and interpreting the diverse approaches and focuses of the assessed visions, as described in the following table.

Cluster	Visions	Description
1	Comprehensive	Broad in scope, addressing multiple purposes and governance
2	Ecosystem-oriented	Focused on conserving nature and managing direct drivers
3	Equity-oriented	Emphasizing equity, empowerment, and quality of life
4	Other	Narrower in scope with less defined purposes and drivers

Data location and description: Cluster column in the database (A)

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.0_visions_database_partial(A)

Step 3: Visions' Themes Analysis

Description: To identify and elaborate on the key themes of vision descriptions, Hugging Face language models were used for text summarization and analysis, combined with a qualitative assessment of the visions (Rothman, 2022).

Method: The methodology followed a structured, step-by-step approach:

- Text extraction

The document is thoroughly read, the main topics and recurring concepts are noted. Then relevant text sections that discuss the concepts and initiatives are gathered. After extraction, the text is organized into manageable segments for analysis through text segmentation.

- The summary

The text is divided into smaller, more manageable chunks that fit within the input size constraints of the model. This process, known as text chunking for summarisation, involves implementing a

function to split the text into chunks, ensuring that each chunk stays within the 1024-token limit for effective summarisation. Using the Hugging Face transformers library, a summarisation pipeline is initialised with a pre-trained language model, facebook/bart-large-cnn. Each text chunk is summarised, and the results are combined into a comprehensive summary. Key themes are identified based on the summarised text. The analysis of the combined summary helps highlight recurring concepts and key points, which are then grouped into broader themes that encapsulate the core messages of the document.

- Validation of identified themes

This involves referring to the original text to identify and cite specific sections, quotes, and examples that support each theme, ensuring that the themes are grounded in the document's content. The elaboration of the themes provides a detailed description and context for each theme. This step involves discussing the significance of each theme, related initiatives, and how it fits into the broader context of visions for transformative change. The final review and synthesis ensure that the themes are comprehensive, non-overlapping, and well-supported. Reviewing the identified themes and their descriptions for coherence and completeness, and making necessary adjustments, ensures clarity and relevance.

Data location and description: Section 2.3.1 characteristics of visions in chapter 2 based on an analysis of the database (A).

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.0_visions_database_partial(A)

Step 4: Radar Plot Visualization

Description: A radar plot was created using the *matplotlib* library to visually represent the mean values of each attribute for each cluster. The radar plot helped to compare the clusters based on the selected attributes.

Data location and description: figures 2.3 and 2.7 in chapter 2

References

Blasius, J. & Greenacre, M. Transformers for Natural Language Processing: Build, train, and fine-tune deep neural network architectures for NLP with Python, Hugging Face, and OpenAI's GPT-3, ChatGPT, and GPT-4 in Visualization and verbalization of data. 2014. Taylor & Francis Group.

Loria, S. (2018). textblob Documentation. Release 0.15, 2.

Miles M.B. & Huberman A.M. Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook. 1994. Sage Publications.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Description
1	1-IPBES_TCA_chapter 2. DMR 2.0_sentiment_clustering_theme_analyses_V2	pdf	DMR
2	2-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.0_visions_ database_analyses_process_v3	jpeg	Flow chart of the process
3	3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.0_visions_database_partial(A)	csv	Database